

Angles of Arrival Estimation with Unitary Partial Propagator

Youssef Khmou, Said Safi

Abstract—In this paper, we investigated the effect of real valued transformation of the spectral matrix of the received data for Angles Of Arrival estimation problem. Indeed, the unitary transformation of Partial Propagator (UPP) for narrowband sources is proposed and applied on Uniform Linear Array (ULA).

Monte Carlo simulations proved the performance of the UPP spectrum comparatively with Forward Backward Partial Propagator (FBPP) and Unitary Propagator (UP). The results demonstrates that when some of the sources are fully correlated and closer than the Rayleigh angular limit resolution of the broadside array, the UPP method outperforms the FBPP in both of spatial resolution and complexity.

Keywords—DOA, Uniform Linear Array, Narrowband, Propagator, Real valued transformation, Subspace, Unitary Operator.

I. INTRODUCTION

DIRECTION OF ARRIVAL estimation (DOA) of impinging electromagnetic or acoustic waves on antenna arrays is an important problem in many fields [1] such as sonar, phased array radar, radio astronomy, Electronic Surveillance Measure (ESM), submarine acoustics, Global System for Mobile (GSM) positioning, geophysics and so on .

Many DOA estimation methods have been proposed in the last two decades such as Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) [2], Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Techniques (ESPRIT) [3] which are subspace based techniques by using the eigen-value decomposition (EVD) or the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the cross correlation matrix of the received signals from the radiating sources in order to construct the sets of signal and noise subspaces. However, when the number of antenna elements is large, the subspace based techniques may require extensive computational load. To overcome this problem, many fast DOA techniques have been established like the Propagator Method (PM) [4], [5], [9], [10] without eigen-decomposition where the steering matrix of the array is divided into two sub- matrices enabling the computation of the propagation operator. In the other hand, when the noise of the antenna sensors is not spatially and temporally uniform, which can be caused by many factors such as temperature, humidity, pressure and vibration, the PM method may fail to detect the Angles Of Arrival (AOA) of the incoming signals, for this reason, a modified version of the PM method [6], we call it Partial Propagator, is derived by using the off diagonal sub-

matrices of the steering matrix, which make it efficient in the presence of colored noise.

In this paper, we present real valued Unitary Partial Propagator (UPP) using unitary transformation matrices in case of incoherent and coherent narrowband sources to estimate their azimuth angles. The simulation results are illustrated to test the efficiency of the proposed transformation that outperforms the Partial Propagator even if the Forward Backward averaging technique is applied to it, moreover the computational complexity of the (UPP) is reduced by factor of four at least [7].

II. PARAMETRIC DATA MODEL

We consider a Uniform Linear Array (ULA) consisting of N isotropic and identical antenna elements as illustrated in Fig. 1 and P sources emitting monochromatic electromagnetic waves with the same carrier frequency f_c . After the acquisition of K snapshots, the received signal vector $X(t) = [X_1(t), X_2(t), \dots, X_N(t)]^T$, with the index $t = 1, 2, \dots, K$ can be written as follows :

$$X(t) = A(\theta)s(t) + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $A(\theta) = [a_1(\theta), a_2(\theta), \dots, a_p(\theta)]^T$ is the array steering matrix, taking the right most element of the ULA as the phase reference, as illustrated in Fig. 1, the steering vector is $a(\theta_i) = [1, e^{-j\mu_i}, \dots, e^{-j(N-1)\mu_i}]^T$, $\mu_i = 2\pi c^{-1} f_c d \sin \theta_i$, d is the inter-element distance and c is the speed of the electromagnetic wave $c = 2.99e + 8 \text{ m/s}$. The sources waveforms and the zero mean ergodic Gaussian noise are denoted respectively by $s(t) = [s_1(t), s_2(t), \dots, s_p(t)]^T$ and $n(t) = [n_1(t), \dots, n_N(t)]^T$. The cross correlation matrix of the received signals can be expressed as:

$$R_{xx} = E\{X(t)X^H(t)\} = A(\theta)R_{ss}A^H(\theta) + \sigma^2 I_N \quad (2)$$

where R_{ss} is the covariance matrix of the source signals, I_N is the identity matrix, σ^2 is the noise variance and $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the conjugate transpose. If we suppose that the number of sensors satisfy the condition $N > 2P$, the set of P steering vectors is linearly independent and the sources signals are not correlated, the array steering matrix can be partitioned into three sub-matrices as follows:

$$A(\theta) = [A_1(\theta), A_2(\theta), A_3(\theta)]^T \quad (3)$$

$A_1(\theta), A_2(\theta)$ are of size $P \times P$ while $A_3(\theta)$ is $(N-2P) \times P$ matrix. We compute the following partial cross correlation matrices:

Youssef Khmou and Said Safi are with Department of Mathematics and Informatics, polydisciplinary faculty Sultan Moulay Slimane University, Beni Mellal, Morocco (e-mail: khmou.y@gmail.com, safi.said@gmail.com).

Fig. 1 Phase interferometry with broadside linear array

$$R_{12} = E\{X(1:P, t)X^H(P+1:2P, t)\} = A_1 R_{ss} A_2^H \quad (4)$$

$$R_{31} = E\{X(2P+1:N, t)X^H(1:P, t)\} = A_3 R_{ss} A_1^H \quad (5)$$

$$R_{32} = E\{X(2P+1:N, t)X^H(P+1:2P, t)\} = A_3 R_{ss} A_2^H \quad (6)$$

such that $X(i:j, t)$ (i.e $t=1, \dots, K$) is the i^{th} to the j^{th} rows of $X(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$. The sub-matrix $A_3(\theta)$ can be calculated by two different equations:

$$R_{32} R_{12}^{-1} A_1 = A_3 R_{ss} A_2^H A_2^{-H} R_{ss}^{-1} A_1^{-1} A_1 = A_3 \quad (7)$$

$$R_{31} R_{21}^{-1} A_2 = A_3 R_{ss} A_1^H A_1^{-H} R_{ss}^{-1} A_2^{-1} A_2 = A_3 \quad (8)$$

Combining (7) and (8) gives:

$$R_{32} R_{12}^{-1} A_1 + R_{31} R_{21}^{-1} A_2 = 2A_3 \quad (9)$$

Using matrix augmentation yields to:

$$[R_{32} R_{12}^{-1} | R_{31} R_{21}^{-1}] - 2I_{N-2P} A(\theta) = 0_{(N-2P) \times P} \quad (10)$$

where I_{N-2P} is an identity matrix, hence we can construct the matrix Q^H that is orthogonal to the steering matrix $A(\theta)$: $Q^H A(\theta) = 0_{(N-2P) \times P}$. The angular spectrum is given by:

$$f(\theta) = \|Q^H a(\theta)\|^{-2} \quad (11)$$

Our contribution, in this paper, lies in the use of real valued covariance matrix R_R instead of complex valued one R_{xx} , that will reduce the computational complexity of the DOAs estimation and enhance the resolution capability of correlated sources. We begin with the definition of complex unitary matrices, let $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, for $N = 2n$ we define:

$$Q_N = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} I_n & jI_n \\ 0_{1 \times n} & -jI_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

For $N = 2n + 1$ we define:

$$Q_N = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} I_n & 0_{n \times 1} & jI_n \\ 0_{1 \times n} & \sqrt{2} & 0_{1 \times n} \\ J_n & 0_{n \times 1} & -jJ_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where I_n is an n identity matrix, $j = \sqrt{-1}$ and J_n is the flipped identity matrix in the left right side direction also called exchange matrix. The unitary matrix satisfies the following properties: $J_N Q_N^* = Q_N$ and $Q_N^H Q_N = J_N$. Next, the following theorem [7] is used for the real valued transformation of the spectral matrix R_{xx} .

Theorem 1: For any Hermitian persymmetric matrix $H \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ such that $J_N H^* J_N = H$, the matrix $W = Q_N^H H Q_N$ is real and symmetric (i.e $W \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ & $W = W^T$).

Proof is presented in [8], using the relations $J_N J_N = I_N$ and $J_N R_{xx}^* J_N = R_{xx}$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} (Q_N^H R_{xx} Q_N)^* &= Q_N^T R_{xx}^* Q_N^* = Q_N^T J_N J_N R_{xx}^* J_N J_N Q_N^* \\ &= Q_N^T J_N R_{xx} J_N Q_N^* = Q_N^H R_{xx} Q_N \end{aligned}$$

However, the matrix R_{xx} in (2) is Hermitian but not persymmetric, the persymmetrization property can be realized with forward backward averaging technique [7]:

$$R_{FB} = \frac{1}{2} (R_{xx} + J_N R_{xx}^* J_N) \quad (14)$$

The real valued matrix is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} R_R &= Q_N^H \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (R_{xx} + J_N R_{xx}^* J_N) \right\} Q_N \quad (15) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (Q_N^H R_{xx} Q_N + Q_N^H J_N R_{xx}^* J_N Q_N) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (Q_N^H R_{xx} Q_N + Q_N^{H*} R_{xx}^* Q_N^*) \\ &= \text{Real}\{Q_N^H R_{xx} Q_N\} \end{aligned}$$

The partial matrices described in (4), (5) and (6) are extracted from the real covariance matrix defined in (15) to construct a real valued set Q_R as in (10) and the new spectrum $f_R(\theta)$ is computed using a new steering vector $a'(\theta) = Q^H a(\theta)$ in (11).

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section is divided into two parts, first we evaluate the performance of the proposed DOA function with fixed Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), in the second time we investigate the performance in the presence of fully correlated sources while considering the inter-element distance as function of the wavelength $d = f(\lambda)$.

A. Modified DOA Function with Uncorrelated Sources

In this part, we consider a Uniform Linear Array (ULA) consisting of $N=11$ isotropic and identical sensors with the same excitation current and zero phase, the inter-element distance is half the wavelength. We assume that there are $P=4$ narrowband and almost equally powered radiating sources (Power ~ 1 watt) that are statistically independent of each other and impinge on the array from directions $\theta_1 = -65^\circ, \theta_2 = 21^\circ, \theta_3 = 25^\circ$ and $\theta_4 = 51^\circ$. The sources signals are complex ergodic Gaussian processes with number of snapshots $K=200$ and the carrier frequency is $f_c = 500$ Mhz which makes the length of the array ULA = 3m. Fig. 2 represents the average

of $L=200$ of Monte Carlo runs of the Unitary Partial Propagator (UPP) when $SNR=2dB$.

Fig. 2 Unitary Partial Propagator (UPP), $SNR=2dB$

Using the same conditions, we compare the UPP function with the Unitary Propagator function (UP) and the complex valued Partial Propagator (PP), Fig. 3 represents the average of $L=200$ runs of the three spectra.

Fig. 3 DOA functions with $SNR=2dB$

The Unitary transformation of both the Propagator (UP) and Partial Propagator (UPP) has increased their resolution power while the Partial Propagator failed to separate the sources located at $[21^\circ, 25^\circ]$. In terms of computational complexity, the Unitary Propagator (UP) has $q(NPK + O(P^3))$ with $q=0.25$, the Partial Propagator (PP) takes $P(N - P)K + O(P^3)$ while the Unitary Partial Propagator (UPP) has the lower complexity which is $q(P(N - P)K + O(P^3))$.

B. Modified DOA Function with Correlated Sources

The problem of correlated sources is treated with many solutions, the two well known methods are the Forward Backward (FB) averaging technique and the spatial smoothing of the cross correlation matrix R_{xx} . To evaluate the Unitary

Partial Propagator, we compare it with Forward Backward Partial Propagator (FBPP) where the decorrelation operation is applied using equation (14) before extracting the partial sub-matrices. In this part, we consider the second and the third sources, whose Angles Of Arrival (AOA) are respectively $\theta_2 = 21^\circ, \theta_3 = 25^\circ$, to be fully correlated $s_2(t) = s_3(t)$ and $s_1(t) \neq s_2(t) \neq s_4(t)$.

The objective of this paragraph is to investigate if there exists an ensemble of values of the inter-element distance in terms of wavelength such that the UPP and FBPP spectra can detect the fully correlated sources. Indeed we consider the inter-element distance as a function of the wavelength $d = f(\lambda)$ with the bounds $d_{min}/\lambda=0.1$ and $d_{max}/\lambda=1$.

Fig. 4 Array Factor of broadside ULA, $d = f(\lambda)$

The variation of the inter-element distance impacts the radiation pattern of the Uniform Linear Array (ULA) precisely the main lobe, Fig. 4 represents the radiation pattern of the broadside ULA ($\theta_{max} = \pi/2$) as function of d . The Rayleigh limit of angular resolution when $d = \lambda/2$ is $\theta_{HPBW} \cong 10^\circ$ where $\theta_{HPBW} = \lambda / d(N - 1)$. The FBPP function is evaluated by taking the average spectrum of $L=150$ Monte Carlo runs for every value of d , as illustrated in the Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Forward Backward Partial Propagator in dB, $d = f(\lambda)$

The first and the fourth sources are well detected and the spectrum is operational in the range $d \in [0.2\lambda, 0.5\lambda]$, the correlated sources are not discerned but located as single source, starting from $d = 0.8\lambda$ the correlated source are well located but side lobes in the spectrum prevent its efficiency. In Fig. 6, we represent the result of the UPP DOA function which is performing, in the range $d \in [0.4\lambda, 0.5\lambda]$ unlike the FBPP, and successful in discerning the fully correlated sources.

Fig. 6 Unitary Partial Propagator in dB, $d = f(\lambda)$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a unitary transformation of Partial Propagator (UPP) operator for narrowband Direction Of Arrival (DOA) estimation using Uniform Linear Array (ULA). In the first time we have compared the UPP spectrum with two functions: the Partial Propagator (PP) and the Unitary Propagator (UP). In the second experiment, we have assumed that half of the sources are fully correlated and we evaluated the (UPP) with the Forward Backward Partial Propagator (FBPP) while the Signal to Noise Ratio is fixed, theoretical results proved that the UPP is successful in discerning the correlated sources.

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Youssef Khmou obtained the B.Sc. degree in Physics and M.Sc. degree from polydisciplinary faculty, in 2010 and from Faculty of Science and Technics Beni Mellal, Morocco, in 2012, respectively. Now he is Ph.D. student and his research interests include statistical signal and array processing and statistical physics.

Said Safi received the B.Sc. degree in Physics (option Electronics) from Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakech, Morocco in 1995, M.Sc. and Doctorate degrees from Chouaib Doukkali University and Cadi Ayyad University, in 1997 and 2002, respectively. He has been a Professor of information theory and telecommunication systems at the National School for applied Sciences, Tangier, Morocco, from 2003 to 2005. Since 2006, he is a Professor of applied mathematics and programming at the Faculty of Science and Technics, Beni Mellal, Morocco. In 2008 he received the Ph.D. degree in Telecommunication and Informatics from the Cadi Ayyad University. His general interests span the areas of communications and signal processing, estimation, time-series analysis, and system identification – subjects on which he has published 14 journal papers and more than 60 conference papers. Current research topics focus on transmitter and receiver diversity techniques for single- and multi-user fading communication channels, and wide-band wireless communication systems